

Analytical Methods

Heat-stable peptide markers for bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen for authenticity testing of minced beef products

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ABSTRACT

Due to the high market value of beef, the beef supply chain is susceptible to economically motivated food fraud. Focusing on the particular risk of offal as an adulterant, a bottom-up proteomics approach was used to identify tryptic, heat-stable peptide markers for the detection, identification, and differentiation of bovine offal in minced beef products. The workflow, which included extensive selectivity testing to rule out cross-selectivities with meat of six other meat-producing animal species (chicken, goat, horse, pig, sheep, turkey) as well as 25 other food ingredients, resulted in the discovery of 17 new peptide markers and the confirmation of five additional peptide markers from the literature: heart (6), kidney (1), kidney/liver (2), liver (3), lung (6), spleen/lung (2), spleen (2). All evaluated peptide markers were heat-stable and detectable in a highly processed model beef matrix, confirming their suitability for use in the development of analytical methods for food authenticity testing.

1. Introduction

According to averaged market data (2021 to 2023), the category “beef and veal” was the most expensive of the three most consumed meat product categories (beef and veal, pigmeat, poultry) in the EU and is projected to retain this position for the foreseeable future (European Commission and Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2023). Consequently, the beef supply chain is considered susceptible to economically motivated food fraud. Robson et al. (2020) analysed a total of 413 food fraud reports from 1997 to 2017 concerning the beef supply chain. Of those 413 reports, 173 (41.9%) were related to adulteration at different stages of the beef supply chain, according to the authors. Minced and otherwise processed beef products, such as burger patties and sausages, must be seen as particularly vulnerable, because processing and seasoning may render undeclared substitutions unrecognisable to the consumer. In addition to the economic loss for the consumer, adulterated foods carry a risk to public health in general (Spink & Moyer, 2011), with both aspects constituting a control point for enforcement authorities in particular.

The substitution, or adulteration, of meat with offal for economic gain has previously been identified as a risk in the production of meat products (Cavin et al., 2018; Shirsath & Henchion, 2021). While figures on offal pricing were not available, offal is generally regarded as cheaper, or likely to be cheaper, than meat in the relevant litera-

ture (Cavin et al., 2018; Grundy et al., 2023; Shirsath & Henchion, 2021). However, the landscape of capable analytical methods available to stakeholders for detecting this type of fraud is still sparsely populated. Grundy et al. (2023) reviewed the analytical methods available for the determination of offal adulterations in meat products, focusing on the identification of methods suitable for food control laboratories. Of the methods reviewed, few could reliably identify the adulterant tissue while also demonstrating the potential for quantitation in processed products. Vishnuraj et al. (2021) reported a microRNA-based method for the determination of chicken offal in processed chicken meat products. While the method detected the addition of selected chicken offal tissues, the pool of testable adulterant tissue types was limited (chicken liver, heart, and gizzard), and detection limits ($\geq 25\%$ meat substitution) would need to be improved for implementation in food control laboratories (Grundy et al., 2023). Vibrational spectroscopy-based methods allow for very fast analyses with minimal to no sample preparation but have limited sensitivity and ability to gather specific information on the adulteration, such as identity or quantity (Al-Jowder et al., 1999, 2002; Fengou et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2017; Morsy & Sun, 2013; Zhao et al., 2014, 2013). A method developed by Black et al. (2019) for the detection of offal in minced beef showed that rapid evaporative ionisation mass spectrometry (REIMS) could likewise be used to distinguish adulterated from unadulterated samples very

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quickly and with suitable sensitivity. However, the method currently cannot provide quantitative results and the required equipment is expensive and much less common in laboratories than triple-quadrupole mass spectrometer (TQ-MS) systems. Grundy et al. (2023) concluded liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) to be a platform with the potential to develop a rapid, high-throughput, sensitive, and potentially quantitative, method to determine offal type and species of origin. They also pointed out that proteomics has excellent potential in terms of robustness and reliability where other techniques have shown to have limitations, and that there is great potential to determine offal tissue markers for the development of LC-MS/MS methods with the largely unique prospect of also allowing species differentiation.

Recent studies have since exploited this potential by developing LC-MS/MS methods based on the detection of heat-stable peptide markers for the determination of liver tissue from pig (Stachniuk, Trzpił, Kozub, Montowska & Fornal, 2023), as well as from rabbit and chicken (Stachniuk, Trzpił, Montowska, Fornal, 2023) in processed meat products of the same species. Furthermore, the possibility of absolute quantitation of rabbit liver peptide markers in processed food via the use of isotope-labelled peptides has been demonstrated (Stachniuk et al., 2024). To the best of our knowledge, similar capabilities are not yet available for the investigation of offal adulteration in the beef supply chain. By our assessment, bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen were considered the most likely candidates for use as meat replacement, taking into consideration the available information on the technological feasibility of processed meat products with intended additions of offal, as well as the organs' contribution to the live animal weight as a measure for the economic viability of their use as an adulterant.

The objective of this study was to identify heat-stable peptide markers for use with common TQ-MS instruments, which would allow the simultaneous detection of bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen in processed meat products. Tissue selectivity was investigated intra-species among the five selected organs, meat, and blood, while inter-species selectivity was investigated regarding meat from other species of interest, namely chicken, goat, horse, pig, sheep, and turkey, as well as common ingredients for minced beef products. Raw and cooked beef matrices, adulterated to 10% (w/w) with the selected bovine organs, were used as a model to investigate the detectability, heat-stability, and overall suitability of peptide marker candidates. This is the first study to identify heat-stable peptide markers for these five bovine offal tissues using a comprehensive proteomics workflow.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Acetone (Ph. Eur., $\geq 99.8\%$, Merck Sigma-Aldrich Supelco, Taufkirchen, Germany), acetonitrile (ACN, $\geq 99.8\%$, Promochem, Wesel, Germany), Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, p.a., J. T. Baker, Center Valley, USA), formic acid (FA, $\geq 99\%$, VWR International, Darmstadt, Germany), hydrochloric acid 37% (HCl, Ph. Eur., Merck Sigma-Aldrich Supelco, Taufkirchen, Germany), thiourea ($\geq 98\%$, Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany), tris(hydroxymethyl)-aminomethane (TRIS, $\geq 99.3\%$, PanReac AppliChem, Darmstadt, Germany), trypsin (sequencing grade, modified, including 50 mM acetic acid reconstitution buffer, Promega, Madison, USA), and water (HPLC grade, Honeywell International, Morris Plains, USA) were procured from the indicated sources. Sodium chloride (NaCl, $\geq 99.5\%$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, $\geq 98\%$), tri-sodium citrate dihydrate (p.a.), and urea ($\geq 99.5\%$) were sourced from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2. Samples

Authentic samples of bovine (*Bos taurus*) tissues (n=6: heart, kidney, liver, lung, spleen, blood; n=7: muscle tissue (=beef)) were acquired fresh from a local slaughterhouse and a local butcher. The blood was citrated upon sampling to avoid coagulation. Meat samples (n=3) from chicken (*Gallus gallus*), goat (*Capra hircus*), horse (*Equus caballus*), pig (*Sus scrofa*), sheep (*Ovis aries*), and turkey (*Meleagris gallopavo*) were acquired from domestic German producers either fresh or frozen. Herbs, spices, and other ingredients commonly used in minced beef products were procured from local and online retailers. More detailed information on the sample material used in the following sections can be found in Supplementary Table S1 under the sample identifier that is provided in parentheses where appropriate. Unless stated otherwise, all samples were processed and prepared for measurement in accordance with Section 2.3. All samples were stored frozen at -18°C .

2.2.1. Sample pools

Samples of species from the exclusion list (Section 2.4.2, without *Homo sapiens*) were pooled by combining defatted homogenised sample material of the respective samples. Meat samples were pooled by species (chicken, goat, horse, pig, sheep, turkey) for a total of six three-component pools. The remaining exclusion list samples were divided into five additional pools of five components each (five-component pools). See Supplementary Table S1 for more details.

2.2.2. Preparation and heat treatment of organ-adulterated model beef matrices

Beef from four animals (B1/1096, B2/1103, B3/1110, B5/1124) as well as heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen from one animal (B4/1112 to 1116) were homogenised using a Grindomix GM 200 laboratory blender (Retsch, Haan, Germany) in 5 s to 10 s intervals at 3000 rpm to 4000 rpm. The beef homogenate batches were combined in a bowl and mixed thoroughly by hand. Adulterated beef matrices were obtained by blending 15 g organ homogenate with 135 g beef homogenate, resulting in batches of adulterated beef homogenate consisting to approximately 10% (w/w) of the respective organ. Each adulterated homogenate was divided into two samples of 40 g (to remain raw) and two samples of 20 g (to be cooked). 150 g of the beef homogenate were divided in the same way to serve as the unadulterated control. The samples to be cooked, contained in 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tubes (outside diameter: 29 mm, wall thickness: ~ 1 mm) closed with screw caps (Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany), were placed in a water bath at 100°C for 30 min. After cooking, the contents were thoroughly mixed with a spatula.

2.3. Sample preparation

2.3.1. Homogenisation and defatting

Organ and meat samples were cut into pieces (0.1 cm^3 to 1 cm^3), avoiding fat, blood vessels, and, in the case of organs, other not obviously organ-specific tissues. Model beef matrices (Section 2.2.2) and all other remaining samples required no such preparation. Meat, organ, and blood samples, as well as model beef matrix samples, were lyophilised. If necessary, samples were homogenised in a "Tube Mill control" (19000 rpm to 25000 rpm for 10 s to 15 s, with or without an interval setting of 5 s) using MT40 disposable grinding chambers (IKA-Werke, Staufen, Germany).

For defatting, 0.5 g to 1 g of the finely grained or powdery sample material was packed into 20 mL extraction cells utilising laboratory wipes (Labsolute, Th. Geyer, Renningen, Germany). The cell contents were then subjected to a pressurised liquid extraction with acetone in a Speed Extractor E-916 (Büchi Labortechnik, Flawil, Switzerland) in two cycles at 50°C and 50 bar with a static time of 5 min. The dried defatted material was transferred together with two 5 mm ceramic beads to 7 mL gasketed tubes for homogenisation (15 s at level 3) in a Minily homogeniser (Bertin Technologies, Montigny-le-Bretonneux, France).

2.3.2. Preparation for mass spectrometry

Protein extraction was performed using buffer U (urea [6 M], thiourea [1 M], TRIS [50 mM], pH 8.2 set using HCl/NaOH) in 1.5 mL tubes with snap cap (LoBind, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany), loaded with 5 mg of defatted sample material, with the exception of model beef matrices (25 mg), three-component pools (3 mg), and five-component pools (15 mg). In the case of pool samples, 0.5 mg alfalfa (501) were added as a positive control, representing a protein contribution to the digestion phase below the lowest estimated level contributed by any single pool component. To each tube, 500 μ L buffer U solution were added, as well as four 1.4 mm ceramic beads to facilitate more effective mixing (5 s to 10 s intervals at level 10 until the sample was suspended) using a lab bench vortexer (Vortex Genie 2, Scientific Industries, Bohemia, USA) for all samples except model beef matrices, for which a Bead Ruptor 24 Elite (Omni International, Kennesaw, USA) was used (4.0 m/s for 30 s). The protein extraction was performed under constant shaking (1400 rpm) for 1 h at 40 °C in a ThermoMixer (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). After cooling to room temperature, the samples were centrifuged for 10 min at 13 523 \times g. A volume of 100 μ L of the supernatant was transferred to fresh 1.5 mL snap cap tubes and diluted with 500 μ L of buffer T (TRIS-HCl [1 M], pH 8.2 set using HCl/NaOH). The diluted protein extracts were mixed with 20 μ L trypsin solution (0.1 g/L in 50 mM acetic acid) and incubated for 18 h at 37 °C. The digestion was stopped by adding 2 μ L of concentrated FA, which was followed by centrifuging for 10 min at 13 523 \times g. Finally, a solid phase extraction (SPE) of the digests, with subsequent concentration and reconstitution, was performed. Chromabond HR-X SPE columns (30 mg/1 mL/45 μ m) from Macherey-Nagel (Düren, Germany) were preconditioned with 1 mL ACN and 1 mL water, loaded with 300 μ L supernatant, and then washed with 1 mL water. The elution step was performed using 2 \times 250 μ L ACN/water (80/20, v/v), collecting the eluate in fresh 1.5 mL snap cap tubes containing 5 μ L DMSO as keeper. The solutions were then concentrated to 5 μ L in a heating block at 50 °C under a gentle N₂-stream, and subsequently reconstituted by adding 50 μ L eluent A (97 % water, 3 % ACN, 0.1 % FA). The reconstituted solutions were loaded onto centrifugal filters (nylon, 0.2 μ m) from VWR International (Radnor, USA) and centrifuged for 2 min at 13 523 \times g. The filtrates were transferred to 1.1 mL conical screw vials (WICOM, Heppenheim, Germany) and stored at -18 °C between measurements.

2.4. Preliminary identification and pre-selection of peptides via high-resolution mass spectrometry

The identification and selection of peptide markers was based on the workflow depicted in Fig. 1, which was adapted from previous works (Häfner et al., 2021; Spörl et al., 2022). Samples of bovine heart (A1/936), kidney (A1/937), liver (A1/938), lung (A2/963), spleen (A2/962), as well as beef (A1/941, A3/964), and bovine blood (A1/942) were processed as described in Section 2.3, preparing three replicates per sample for the initial search for peptide marker candidates.

2.4.1. Liquid chromatography high-resolution mass spectrometry

The liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS) assembly consisted of a Dionex Ultimate 3000 high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA), coupled to a maXis quadrupole time-of-flight (QToF) high-resolution mass spectrometer (HR-MS) (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). Chromatographic separation was performed by a Nucleosil 100-3 C18HD reversed-phase column (125 mm \times 2 mm, particle size 3 μ m, Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany), kept at 40 °C, in combination with a gradient from eluent A (97 % water, 3 % ACN, 0.1 % FA) to eluent B (10 % water, 90 % ACN, 0.1 % FA) at a constant flow rate of 0.25 mL/min with the following gradient levels connected by linear ramps: 0 min to 3 min: 2 % B; 33 min: 60 % B; 34 min to 44 min: 100 % B; 45 min to 52 min: 2 % B. A volume of 2 μ L of the sample solution prepared according to Section 2.3.2

Fig. 1. Workflow for the identification of peptide markers, outlining the process from initial QToF data to the final marker peptides. (a) first pass (blue); (b) second pass (red). The second pass revisited QToF data for the groups kidney/spleen, liver/spleen, and kidney/liver/spleen, as well as a “reserve” spleen marker and suitable theoretical peptides from plastin-2 (spleen). Numbers indicate the number of peptides proceeding to the next step; ¹ Durose and Billett (2010); “theoretical peptides” = suitable tryptic peptides from selected proteins, which had not been detected yet; * five of seven literature peptides were also detected in the QToF data (4074).

was injected into the instrument for data-dependent MS/MS acquisition (Auto-MS/MS) in positive electro spray ionisation (ESI) mode. The ESI interface and acquisition settings were largely adopted from Jira and Münch (2019), with a deviating drying gas (N₂) temperature of 200 °C and collision energies (CEs) in the range of 21 eV to 50 eV chosen by the instrument in accordance with the isolation and fragmentation list for peptides provided by Bruker (Supplementary Table S2). The acquisition was performed using a precursor selection window from > 400 m/z to < 1400 m/z, excluding singly charged precursors.

2.4.2. Data analysis

The data acquired on the QToF instrument was subjected to de novo peptide sequencing and a database search in PEAKS Studio 10.0 (Bioinformatics Solutions, Waterloo, Canada), including false discovery rate (FDR) estimation via an enhanced target-decoy method (Zhang et al., 2012). The de novo sequencing parameters were as follows: error tolerance (precursor & product ion mass): 0.025 Da; accepted charge range: 2 to 3; tryptic peptides, excluding peptides with missed cleavages. Peptide sequences were searched in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) protein database (downloaded: 2023-03-31), limited to *Bos taurus*. The putatively identified peptide sequences had to meet

the following criteria, to ensure sequencing reliability: an FDR $\leq 1\%$ for peptides found in the database (database-matched), or a minimum amino acid identity average local confidence (ALC) of 85% for de novo only peptides. Both sets of peptides were imported into JMP 17.1.0 (JMP Statistical Discovery, Cary, USA), where they were sorted into uniqueness categories depending on their occurrence within the samples. Peptides occurring in any replicate of beef or blood, and peptides shorter than 7 and longer than 20 amino acids, were excluded from further consideration, as were peptides containing cysteine, post-translational modifications, mutations, or decoy sequences. Initially, candidate peptides had to be present in all three replicates of their target tissue in order to be considered further. Exceptions from this were made for heart in general, and for spleen in the case of plastin-2, the peptides of which needed only to be present in one replicate (Section 3.2). The thus preselected peptides, as well as seven peptides from Durose and Billett (2010), were subjected to a database search via the protein basic local alignment search tool (BLAST) (NCBI, <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) against the taxonomic groups Mammalia, Sauropsida, and Viridiplantae (non-redundant protein sequences database, accessed: 2023-09-21 to 2023-10-26, and 2024-02-23; settings see Supplementary Figure S1). Tryptic BLAST database hits (100% sequence match) for a peptide or one of its leucine/isoleucine isomers in the following species led to the exclusion of that peptide from further consideration (exclusion list): chicken (*Gallus gallus*), goat (*Capra hircus*), horse (*Equus caballus*), human (*Homo sapiens*), pig (*Sus scrofa*), sheep (*Ovis aries*), turkey (*Meleagris gallopavo*), and any member of Viridiplantae relevant for food production. Included in this search were not-analytically-observed tryptic peptides (“theoretical peptides”) of three heart proteins and one spleen protein. Theoretical peptides of a protein were identified by aligning the complete *Bos taurus* sequence of the target protein with the corresponding sequences of the animal species from the exclusion list to find tryptic sequences unique to *Bos taurus*.

2.5. Peptide synthesis and multiple reaction monitoring parameter optimization

The peptide synthesis employed Fmoc-based chemistry on a Liberty Blue Microwave Peptide Synthesiser (CEM, Kamp-Lintfort, Germany) with subsequent purification. All 52 peptide marker candidates (Section 3.2) were synthesised, purified, and had their identities checked according to the protocol previously published by Häfner et al. (2021). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) parameters (declustering potential (DP), CE, cell exit potential (CXP)) were optimised according to the same protocol, with the following stipulations: precursor charge: 2 to 3; minimum product ion m/z : 300; exclude product ions whose m/z falls within ± 10 units of their precursor's m/z . The five most abundant, theoretically explainable, mass transitions for each peptide were compiled for further use. In this process, the less abundant partner of any a_n - b_n ion pair was discarded, as was the less abundant partner of any pair 17 u or 18 u apart, if the necessary elimination of ammonia or water seemed plausible based on the amino acid sequence.

2.6. Identity, selectivity, and heat-stability testing via low-resolution mass spectrometry

The low resolution LC-MS system used for enhanced product ion (EPI) scan, MRM, and scheduled MRM (sMRM) experiments consisted of a Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC system (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA) coupled to a QTrap 5500 (Sciex, Framingham, USA) MS. The following settings were the same for all experiments on the QTrap instrument: injection volume: 2 μ L; ESI mode: positive; ion source temperature: 430 °C; ion spray voltage: 3.9 kV; nebuliser gas (N_2) pressure: 40 psi; auxiliary gas (N_2) pressure: 60 psi; curtain gas (N_2) pressure: 40 psi; entrance potential (EP): 10 V.

Unless stated otherwise, samples were processed to the ready-to-measure solutions according to Section 2.3 and were also measured spiked for establishing a reference. Spiked samples were prepared by combining the ready-to-measure sample solution with a mixture of the relevant synthesised peptides (Section 2.5). All MRM and sMRM measurements were performed according to Section 2.6.2. EPI experiments were performed according to Section 2.6.1 and only with unspiked samples, using the ready-to-measure solutions of the organs prepared under Section 2.4.

To confirm the amino acid sequence of the peptides, three replicates each of bovine heart (A1/936), kidney (A1/937), liver (A1/938), lung (A2/963), and spleen (A2/962) were prepared for MRM measurement as described in Section 2.3, except that the three post-SPE concentrates per matrix were reconstituted in the same 50 μ L solvent volume, thus increasing concentrations and providing one ready-to-measure solution per matrix to be injected in triplicate. The above-mentioned organ samples, in addition to beef (A1/941), bovine blood (A1/942), and alfalfa (501), were also measured as single injections via sMRM for the initial tissue-selectivity experiment. For the follow-up experiment, complete sets of organs, blood, and beef from five additional bovine individuals (B1–B5/1091 to 1125) were measured via sMRM in duplicate injections, using a spiked spleen and a spiked alfalfa solution from a previous experiment as reference. Negative testing against the exclusion list (Section 2.4.2, without *Homo sapiens*) was performed using the pooled samples (Section 2.2.1), measured via sMRM in duplicate injections. To confirm the success of the sample preparation for negative samples, the following peptide markers from the literature were used: for alfalfa: VEGGLSIMSPPER, FNLEAGDIMR (Spörl et al., 2021); for bovine blood: VGGHAAEYGAELER, AAVTAFWGK (Zhang et al., 2020); for all types of meat: LDEAEQLALK, IQLVEELDR (Häfner et al., 2023). For the heat-stability test, two replicates each of the raw and cooked, adulterated and unadulterated model beef matrix samples (Section 2.2.2) were measured via sMRM. Spiked reference samples were in this case prepared from only one replicate per sample.

2.6.1. Settings for the acquisition of product ion spectra

Chromatographic conditions were identical to those described in Section 2.4.1 except that a shortened gradient with a steeper slope was used (total run time: 35 min). The QTrap was operating in the EPI scan mode (Raffaelli & Saba, 2023), employing the linear ion trap with the following experiment-specific settings: DP: 70 V; CE: 35 eV; CE spread: ± 15 eV; scan rate: 10 000 Da/s; ion trap fill time: 60 ms. Predicted spectra for comparison were generated using the online tool “MS-Product” (UCSF, <https://prospector.ucsf.edu/prospector>, accessed: 2023-12-02 and 2024-06-24), limited to y -, b - and a -ions.

2.6.2. LC-MS/MS settings for MRM- and sMRM-experiments

Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Nucleodur C18 Gravity-SB reversed-phase column (50 mm \times 2 mm, particle size 1.8 μ m, Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany), kept at 40 °C. Eluents were identical to those described in Section 2.4.1 and ran at a constant flow rate of 0.50 mL/min as a gradient consisting of the following levels connected by linear ramps: 0 min to 2 min: 2% B; 15 min: 45% B; 15 min to 22 min: 100% B; 22 min to 28 min: 2% B. The QTrap employed optimised values for DP, CE, and CXP (Section 2.5). For sMRM, the following additional settings were used: target scan time: 0.500 s (maximum projected cycle time out of all experiments: 0.914 s); detection window widths: 60 s to 180 s; minimum dwell time: 10 ms. The parameters of the final sMRM method can be found in Table 1.

2.6.3. Peptide detection and calculation of signal-to-noise ratios

If co-eluting peaks with correct retention times (± 0.10 min of spiked samples) were found for all mass transitions of a given peptide, it was considered present in the matrix in question, provided that all transitions showed a signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio ≥ 3 , and that unexplained shifts in peak area ratios compared to spiked samples did not

Table 1
Parameters of the final sMRM method. Product ions are provided in descending order of peak area.

label	sequence	t _R [min]	precursor m/z (z)	DP [V]	product ion m/z (id)	CE [eV]	CXP [V]
heart1	TSLAGGSR	0.36	374.7 (2+)	56	447.2 (y5) / 560.3 (y6) / 302.2 (b3)	19/17/17	26/28/16
heart2	SGGSTAGDTVPAPPV ¹	5.45	783.4 (2+)	141	733.4 (y7) / 565.3 (y5) / 833.4 (b10)	37/35/31	36/26/40
heart3	SIFTVEGAER	6.13	554.8 (2+)	91	454.7 (y8 ²⁺) / 908.4 (y8) / 432.2 (y4)	21/21/29	20/46/22
heart4	IMDAQTTFAGGYR	6.45	715.8 (2+)	136	360.2 (b3) / 872.4 (y8) / 771.4 (y7)	35/31/35	20/42/42
heart5	VYLFELR	7.98	470.3 (2+)	61	677.4 (y5) / 564.3 (y4) / 376.2 (b3)	19/21/17	34/28/24
heart6	ELWQNIYDLEAEK	9.12	825.9 (2+)	56	867.4 (y7) / 704.8 (y11 ²⁺) ^a / 1094.5 (y9)	35/35/35	40/34/54
kidney1	YENVQPAGSFK	4.87	620.3 (2+)	76	606.3 (y6) ^b / 407.2 (b3) / 734.4 (y7)	33/31/27	28/20/32
kidney/liver1	YGGSYFPK	5.09	459.7 (2+)	106	755.4 (y7) / 698.4 (y6) / 391.2 (y3)	19/19/29	38/36/20
kidney/liver2	MILQQNYTSLR	6.70	683.9 (2+)	181	561.8 (y9 ²⁺) / 881.4 (y7) / 1009.5 (y8)	29/31/33	26/54/50
liver1	SVTEFNGDVTSTMTK ¹	6.54	859.4 (2+)	146	766.4 (y14 ²⁺) / 668.3 (y6) / 1040.5 (y10)	35/47/37	40/40/50
liver2	AADNIGYPVMIR	7.23	660.3 (2+)	96	835.4 (y7) / 615.4 (y5) / 485.2 (b5)	27/27/25	40/30/22
liver3	FSLDQLITHVLPLEK	10.90	585.0 (3+)	26	486.3 (y4) / 759.9 (y13 ²⁺) / 803.5 (y14 ²⁺) ^c	31/21/23	22/44/36
lung1	HQVLQSQGVLR ¹	3.66	632.9 (2+)	41	999.6 (y9) / 900.5 (y8) / 347.2 (b6 ²⁺)	31/35/37	54/40/18
lung2	QSSSTSSFGGMGGGSMR	5.18	810.8 (2+)	86	564.3 (y6) / 956.4 (y10) / 1043.4 (y11)	41/41/41	30/50/50
lung3	SSYGAPVGTGIR	5.19	582.8 (2+)	110	699.4 (y7) / 466.2 (b5) / 495.8 (y10 ²⁺)	29/23/23	34/22/24
lung4	LQGSVLAUGEK ¹	5.48	550.8 (2+)	106	859.5 (y9) / 333.2 (y3) / 432.2 (y4)	23/39/37	40/16/22
lung5	SPEENEAIVSIVK ¹	6.90	707.9 (2+)	136	314.1 (b3) / 446.3 (y4) / 545.4 (y5)	39/39/37	16/20/26
lung6	TGLFTLHSELMVTPAR	8.16	591.7 (3+)	81	444.3 (y4) / 543.3 (y5) / 343.2 (y3)	25/27/25	20/30/24
spleen/lung1	GSVSDEEMLELR	6.96	682.8 (2+)	101	417.2 (y3) / 1121.5 (y9) / 530.3 (y4)	29/29/33	20/54/26
spleen/lung2	YTLNILEDIGGGQK	9.15	760.9 (2+)	141	916.5 (y9) / 446.2 (y5) / 803.4 (y8)	37/51/37	42/24/48
spleen1	VPVDWSR	5.02	429.7 (2+)	81	380.2 (y6 ²⁺) / 563.3 (y4) / 448.2 (y3)	21/25/33	22/26/22
spleen2	EITENLMTTGDLDQDGK	7.36	940.4 (2+)	131	1049.5 (y10) / 847.4 (y8) / 319.2 (y3)	43/41/63	50/40/16
Evaluation incomplete (Section 3.5):							
pmc1	VGGHIAAPR ¹	0.44	439.3 (2+)	126	414.2 (y4) / 527.3 (y5) / 389.7 (y8 ²⁺)	29/29/25	32/32/22
pmc2	VFSTNGQSVNFDAIK ¹	7.23	813.9 (2+)	111	893.5 (y8) / 707.4 (y6) / 1078.6 (y10)	37/37/37	40/48/54
pmc3	ETVLDIVPTDIHQK	7.53	536.6 (3+)	26	419.7 (y7 ²⁺) / 583.3 (y10 ²⁺) / 838.4 (y7)	23/17/21	20/26/54
pmc4	ATVLLADINDFSTVNDVYK	9.78	700.0 (3+)	91	385.2 (b4) / 925.5 (y8) / 569.4 (b6)	27/30/21	20/40/30

EP: 10 V. Possible alternative product ion identities: ^a y6 (704.3), ^b a5 (606.3), ^c b14²⁺ (803.9). ¹ Peptide from Durose and Billett (2010); pmc1–pmc4: peptide marker candidates pending final evaluation. The provided t_R settings are based on observations in pure organ matrices.

exceed ± 15%. The S/N ratios were calculated based on the exported raw x/y data of the individual extracted ion chromatograms. A representative baseline window before or after the peak of interest, 13 data points wide, was defined as the noise region, while the highest signal intensity of the peak of interest was defined as the signal. The S/N ratio was then calculated according to Eq. (1), using 3σ for estimating zero-to-peak noise (European Commission et al., 2016). A set of example chromatograms for some peptide detection scenarios is shown in Supplementary Figure S2.

$$S/N = \frac{(S - \bar{z})}{3\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where:

S = maximum signal intensity of the peak of interest

\bar{z} = average noise signal intensity

σ = corrected standard deviation of the noise region

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Selection of target tissues

In the selection process of the offal tissues to be investigated, we first considered information on what types of offal were being legitimately used in meat products, to gain insight into established practices. Out of all bovine tissues classifiable as offal, we started our search among internal organs due to their general compositional similarity to meat in terms of protein and fat content, and their live body weight percentage (Nollet & Toldrá, 2011), which made them appear as likely candidates for use in economically motivated food fraud. Lynch et al. (2018) reported the culinary use of heart, kidney, liver, lung, pancreas, and tripe (stomachs) in meat products. Shirsath and Henchion (2021) added intestines to the list, and evidence for the use of spleen was found in a South African study on the acceptability of offal-containing sausage formulations (Magoro et al., 2012). Starting with this list of

tissues, we looked at the viability of their use as adulterants from the standpoints of economy and food technology. Tripe and intestines were excluded, since the necessary extensive cleaning procedures would, in our opinion, reduce the economic viability and therefore the likelihood of their systematic use for food fraud in the EU. As comparable and representative figures for bovine offal prices in the EU were not available, the economic viability of the remaining offal tissues could not be evaluated directly. Instead, the percentage of live body weight was used as a proxy, presuming that a higher percentage would make a fraud operation more profitable and thus more likely. Taking into account the mean live body weight percentages of the remaining organs for adult cattle reported by Lin et al. (2020) revealed the following order: liver (1.23%), lungs (0.77%), heart (0.40%), kidneys (0.21%), spleen (0.18%), pancreas (0.09%). Pancreas, contributing the lowest percentage to the live weight out of the selection, was consequently considered the least likely to be used as an adulterant and it was therefore excluded to focus time and resources on more probable scenarios. Regarding the technological feasibility of the five remaining organs, meaningful single-organ data was again limited. A recent study by Douglas et al. (2024) investigated the effects of adding bovine heart to unseasoned beef burger patties at levels of 0, 6, 12 and 18% on selected technological and sensory properties of the product. The authors reported that, while differences in sensory attributes of beef burgers containing 6% bovine heart could be detected by consumers, these beef burgers had the greatest numerical values in all sensory areas, suggesting that adding 6% or less of beef heart might be a viable option. That study demonstrated the technological feasibility of adding bovine heart to burger patties and further demonstrated the potential to do so without raising the suspicion of consumers even when no seasoning or other additives are involved. The technological feasibility of using the other organs as adulterants in minced beef products was assumed in the absence of definitive data. While kidney, liver, lung, and spleen are expected to be harder to incorporate into a product than heart due to them being less similar to meat, it is nevertheless possible

Fig. 2. Venn-Diagram showing the distribution of the 4020 database-matched and 54 de novo only peptides among the organs according to the initial QToF data. Overlap with beef and bovine blood is not shown. Please note that this data is subject to misclassifications due to the nature of the data gathering process as described in Section 3.4 and only serves to illustrate the complexity of the starting point.

that fraudsters have, with the use of additives and other ingredients, found formulations which yield their desired benefits as well as a marketable product. The aspect of off-flavours (Luo et al., 2022) was, for the same reason, not included in the considerations. In the end, bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen were selected as the target organs for our study.

3.2. Search for peptide marker candidates

A bottom-up proteomics approach was used to find tryptic, heat-stable peptide markers suitable for the detection and identification of bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen in minced beef products. Trypsin was chosen for its specific cleavage at lysine and arginine, producing peptides suitable for MS analysis. Fig. 1 illustrates the peptide marker identification workflow, from the initial QToF experiments to the final peptide markers. The analytical search for peptide marker candidates was supplemented by a literature search for peptides reported to have suitable selectivity. To the best of our knowledge, the work by Durose and Billett (2010) contains the only published peptides with the potential to fulfil this requirement, listing the following peptides as tissue-specific for the indicated organs, as well as species-specific amongst bovine, ovine, and porcine samples: heart (SGGSTAGDTVPA-PPVVR; troponin I, cardiac muscle), liver (SVTEFNGDVTSTMTK; fatty acid-binding protein, liver), lung (LQGSVLAVGEK, HQLVLSQGVLR, VFSTNGQSVNFDIAIK, SPEENEAIVSIVK, VGGHIAAPR; all: pulmonary surfactant-associated protein A precursor). In order to find additional peptide markers for the five target tissues, tryptic digests of authentic tissue samples were analysed via HPLC-HR-MS/MS (Section 2.4). The results were subjected to de novo sequencing, which yielded a total of 4074 distinct putative peptide sequences for the five selected organs, mostly made up of database-matched peptides (4020), including five of the seven literature peptides. The few de novo only sequences (54) were retained as a fallback option with lower priority. Fig. 2 shows the distribution of the 4074 peptides among the organs as it presented itself in the QToF data.

Up to the tissue-selectivity testing (Section 3.4.1), the subsequent steps in the workflow were carried out in two passes, differing only in the criteria applied in the first selection step (Fig. 1, “Selection 1”). For the first pass, with the exception of heart, only peptides which were present in all three replicate samples but not in any replicate of beef, blood or any of the other examined organs were investigated further, to promote the selectivity of the peptides. Since only five heart peptides showed the necessary species-specificity in the BLAST search that followed, this requirement was relaxed for heart so that a peptide only needed to be present in one replicate. The pool of heart peptides was further extended by surveying the sequences of three promising proteins apparent in the heart replicates (myosin-binding protein C cardiac-type; troponin I cardiac muscle; troponin T cardiac muscle) for suitable tryptic peptides not found in the QToF data (theoretical peptides). The second pass was prompted by later results for spleen during the initial phase of bovine tissue-selectivity testing (Section 3.4.1), whereafter only one of the original spleen peptides, targeting the protein platin-2 (NP_001029892.1), remained. Although later adjusted somewhat by the results of additional individuals, the picture provided by this first individual suggested similarities between kidney, liver, and spleen, which promised to yield peptide markers for spleen together with kidney and/or liver (see Fig. 2). Thus, before continuing the tissue-selectivity testing, we returned to the beginning of the workflow and searched for peptides originating from platin-2 as well as peptides selective for the following organ groups in the QToF data: kidney/liver/spleen, kidney/spleen, liver/spleen (Fig. 1, “second pass”). Occurrence in one of the three replicates was considered sufficient. This pool was extended by surveying the sequence of platin-2 for theoretical peptides.

After combining all aforementioned peptides with those found in Durose and Billett (2010), further constraints were applied, incorporating some quality features recommended by DIN EN 17644 (German Institute for Standardisation, 2022; length: 7 to 20 amino acids; no cysteine) as well as the following criteria: no post-translational modifications, no mutations, no decoy sequences. The length range of 7 to 20 amino acids had previously been found to be a good compromise between peptide specificity, ionisation yield, and reproducibility (Pilolli et al., 2020). The thus filtered peptides were searched in the NCBI non-redundant protein sequences database using protein BLAST. A total of 402 peptides were searched, comprised of 390 peptides present in the QToF data (including five literature peptides), 10 theoretical peptides and the two remaining literature peptides. Sequences occurring in species from the exclusion list (Section 2.4.2) were discarded. However, it should be noted that such an occurrence would not necessarily pose a problem, depending on the final application of the markers and the exact tissues containing these peptides in the excluded species. Since we aimed to maximise the utility of the final markers, we opted to exclude any potential cross-selectivity with relevant species irrespective of the tissue type. The consideration of humans in this context is owed to the possibility of contamination of food items or samples. Horse was considered relevant due to its history as an adulterant in meat products (Cavin et al., 2018). The remaining animal species were chosen to cover the most consumed meat-producing animal categories in the EU besides cattle, namely pig, poultry, as well as sheep and goat (European Commission and Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2023), with the poultry category made up mainly of chicken, followed by turkey. The protein BLAST search yielded the following numbers of suitable peptides for their primary target tissues: heart (23, including two de novo only), kidney (12), liver (11), lung (10, including one de novo only), and spleen (first pass: 10, second pass: 7). These 73 peptides (Table 2) were subjected to a targeted EPI analysis to verify their presence in the organs independently of the non-targeted results, and to confirm their detectability on the QTrap instrument intended for subsequent experiments (Section 2.6.1). Solely the heart de novo only peptide STA(L/I)SD(L/I)HAHK was not detected in the EPI scan and was therefore discarded.

Table 2

Putative peptide sequences after the BLAST screening, sorted by their primary target tissue and target protein. Shown are the 66 peptides from the first pass and the seven peptides from the second pass (Fig. 1). The 22 final heat-stable peptide markers are shown in bold. The identity of crossed-out entries is considered doubtful.

primary target	putative sequence	a	b	c	d	protein	NCBI accession
heart	VLP S AI V QSV G V S AGR	-	-	3	-	apoptosis-inducing factor 1, mitochondrial	NP_001179913.1
	YSALFLGMAYGAK	x	x			ATP synthase subunit e, mitochondrial	NP_788812.1
	ERPAPFYHHLR	x	x			cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6A2, mitochondrial precursor	NP_776947.1
	TPYHDVNVITIR	x	x			isocitrate dehydrogenase [NAD] subunit alpha, mitochondrial precursor	NP_777069.1
	AHNLGAGPPVTTK	-	x				
	EPVLI P RPGITYELPK	-	x				
	IMDAQTTFAGGYR	-	-	-	-		
	SAEVAAGSSAVFEAETER	-	x				
	SIFTVEGAER	-	-	-	-	myosin-binding protein C, cardiac-type	NP_001070004.1
	TSLAGGSR	-	-	-	-		
	VEDMEDK	-	x				
	VFSHNTVGP S DTAATTK	-	x				
	VYLFELR	-	-	-	-		
	YSLAAEGTR	x	x				
	LGWVRPDLGDL S K	-	-	3	-	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 8	NP_787020.1
	QAEHS AK	-	-	2	-	plectin isoform X1	XP_024857673.1
	LEDAPAVFELAEK	-	x			tetratricopeptide repeat protein 21A isoform X1	XP_024838909.1
	EDHELLRPATT T QR	-	x				
	ISGLIEGAMY Y FR	-	x			titin isoform X1	XP_059736125.1
	SGGSTAGDTPAPPVVR ¹	-	-	-	-	troponin I, cardiac muscle	NP_001035607.1
	ELWQNIYDLEAEK	-	-	-	-	troponin T, cardiac muscle	NP_777196.1
	STA(L/I)SD(L/I)HAHK	-		1	-	dn	dn
YYGAEA(L/D)ER	-	x			dn	dn	
kidney	ATVLLADINDFSTVNDVYK	-	-	-	x	2-iminobutanoate/2-iminopropanoate deaminase	NP_001029380.1
	MILQQNYTSLR	-	-	-	-	acyl-coenzyme A synthetase ACSM1, mitochondrial	NP_777107.1
	VLWEDPAR	-	x			dehydrogenase/reductase SDR family member 4	NP_777247.2
	ETVLDIVPTD H QK	-	-	-	x	fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase 1	NP_001029619.1
	ALATQLPVLPR	-	x			fumarylacetoacetate hydrolase domain-containing protein 2	NP_991359.1
	YGGSYFFK	-	-	-	-	glycine amidinotransferase, mitochondrial precursor	NP_001039343.1
	EIIPLAAEYDK	-	-	3	-	medium-chain specific acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, mitochondrial precursor	NP_001068703.1
	LLJHQGISFLLAEMAMK	x	-	3	-		
	VAGGPQMIQSLD G TR	-	-	3	-	methanethiol oxidase	NP_001039513.1
	IPATIVLPEGTSVK	-	x			serine dehydratase-like	NP_001092465.1
	YENVQPAGSFK	-	-	-	-		
	ATQAHENIHSSGATGK	-	-	3	-	zeta-crystallin	NP_776450.2
	FSLDQLITHVLPLEK	-	-	-	-	alcohol dehydrogenase 1C	NP_001193316.1
	AADNIGYPMIR	-	-	-	-	carbamoyl-phosphate synthase [ammonia], mitochondrial	NP_001179187.1
THFSGDVQR	-	-	3	-	catalase	NP_001030463.1	
IIPGVVDGIFLPK	-	x			cocaine esterase precursor	NP_001029432.1	
liver	AIDGLNSNMR	-	-	3	-		
	LNDGHFIPVLGFGTFAPR	-	-	3	-	dihydrodiol dehydrogenase 3	NP_851370.1
	YNELLGVGHPEYPFVEEY	-	x				
	SVTEFNGDVTSTMTK ¹	-	-	-	-	fatty acid-binding protein, liver	NP_787011.1
	GLDFPNLPYLIDGAHR	x	-	3	-	glutathione S-transferase mu 1	NP_001073823.1
	VYGTVMHMHN G PNFLK	-	x			glycine N-acyltransferase	NP_803479.1
	VTVDAPVSSVALR	-	-	3	-	regucalcin	NP_776382.1
	TGLFTLHSELMVTPAR	-	-	-	-	advanced glycosylation end product-specific receptor precursor	NP_776407.1
	QSSSTSSFGMGGGSMR	-	-	-	-	keratin, type I cytoskeletal 19	NP_001015600.1
	SSYGAPVGTGIR	-	-	-	-	keratin, type II cytoskeletal 7	NP_001039876.1
lung	NSNLGAAHEELQQSR	-	-	3	-	lamin	NP_001029225.1
	HQVLQSQGVLR ¹	-	-	-	-		
	LQGSVLAVGEK ¹	-	-	-	-		
	SPEENEAIVSIVK ¹	-	-	-	-	pulmonary surfactant-associated protein A precursor	NP_001071306.2
	VFTNGQSVNFDAIK ¹	-	-	-	x		
	VGGHIAAPR ¹	-	-	-	x		
	(L/I)DDQPD(L/D)GE(L/I)NSFDK	-	x			dn	dn
	LAMQEFMILPVGAENFR ²	x	-	3	-	alpha-enolase	NP_776474.2
spleen	HVTLEQPR	-	-	3	-	beta-2-microglobulin precursor	NP_776318.1
	YGPIVPIIR	-	-	3	-	cathelicidin-5 precursor	NP_776935.1
	VSSLPQVTVK ²	-	-	3	-	cathepsin D	XP_005227352.1
	FLPGPLFMK	-	-	3	-	glutathione S-transferase Mu 1	NP_787019.1
	DVQQTLSPGDELYK	-	-	3	-		
	GYLTPNYEVK	x	-	3	-		
	IIQQWPHYR	-	-	3	-	peptidoglycan recognition protein 1 precursor	NP_776998.1
	QAQNVQYYHVR	-	-	3	-		
	VPPASALR	-	-	4	-		
	EITENLMTTGDLDQDGK ²	-	-	-	-		
	GSVDEEMLELR ²	-	-	-	-		
	VNDDTIVSWVNETLK ²	-	-	4	-	plastin-2	NP_001029892.1
	VPVDWSR ²	-	-	-	-		
	YTLNILEDIGGGQK	-	-	-	-		
NEAAINEIMEDLDTNV D K ^{2,3}	-	-	3	-	protein S100-A9	NP_001039793.1	
NMADQIIQEISGQIQSK ²	-	-	3	-	transketolase	NP_001003906.1	

Columns a–d: “x” = true; “-” = false; black cell = not applicable; column “a”: hypothetical/predicted BLAST hit in at least one species from the exclusion list (Section 2.4.2); column “b”: peptide which was not synthesised and remained in reserve; column “c”: excluded from further investigation due to: 1 = not found in EPI scan; 2 = identity doubtful; 3 = detected in beef and/or blood; 4 = poor chromatographic behaviour; column “d”: final evaluation incomplete. ¹ Peptide from Durose and Billett (2010); ² peptide evaluated during second workflow pass; ³ revisited reserve peptide; dn: de novo only peptide.

In preparation for the synthesis, the peptides were prioritised according to their performance thus far, and under the provision of preserving a diverse set of target proteins. With at least three peptides per tissue or species being used and recommended in the literature (Jira & Münch, 2019; Li et al., 2018), our goal was to end up with a minimum of three peptide markers per organ, ideally targeting at least two different proteins to allow for more robustness in any future analytical method based on those markers. During the first pass it was decided to limit the maximum number of peptides per organ to nine, in order to strike a balance between the number of peptides and the time spent on the synthesis process. The peptides per organ were considered in descending order of their maximum peak area among the three replicates of the QToF Auto-MS/MS experiment, with the three highest-scoring peptides and the previously mentioned peptides reported by Durose and Billett (2010) being selected for synthesis outright without consideration of other criteria. The remaining peptides were differentiated firstly by EPI spectrum quality and secondly by sequence length, favouring higher perceived quality and shorter sequences in case of similar peak areas. Peptides with poor EPI spectrum quality were excluded, affecting, amongst others, three of the 11 liver peptides. In the case of heart, additional factors had to be considered. The 23 heart peptides divided themselves into three groups. Group 1: found in all three replicates of the QToF experiment (5/23); group 2: found in only one replicate of the QToF experiment (11/23); group 3: theoretical peptides only observed in the EPI scan at this point (7/23). In accordance with the criteria applied for the other organs, the three database-matched members of group 1 were selected for synthesis (SGGSTAGDTVPAPPVVR, VYLFELR, IMDAQTTFAGGYR), adding “myosin-binding protein C cardiac-type” and “troponin I cardiac muscle” as target proteins. Groups 2 and 3 were considered as being equivalent in terms of their potential going forward, but could not be compared directly on the basis of QToF peak area. Therefore, it was decided to select three peptides each from groups 2 and 3, with group 2 being evaluated in the same way as described earlier in this paragraph, and group 3, lacking QToF peak area and representing only two target proteins (myosin-binding protein C cardiac type; troponin T cardiac muscle), being assessed firstly based on the targeted protein, and secondly based on EPI spectrum quality and sequence length. This led to the following peptides being selected from heart group 2: QAEEISAK (plectin isoform X1), VLPSAIVQSVGSAGR (apoptosis-inducing factor 1), LGWVRPDLGDLSK (NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 8). An impasse between LGWVRPDLGDLSK and YSALFLGMAYGAK (ATP synthase subunit e, mitochondrial) was resolved in favour of the former by considering the BLAST result of a predicted hit in goat as a reason to deprioritise the latter. From group 3, ELWQNIYDLEAEK (troponin T cardiac muscle) was selected outright as the only peptide from this target protein among the 21 database-matched peptides for heart. The two remaining positions for group 3 were filled by TSLAGGSR and SIFTVEGAER (both: myosin-binding protein C cardiac type), since they had the shortest sequences of the remaining group 3 peptides, which all targeted the same protein. During the second pass, all eight peptides available at this stage were synthesised, including the one spleen peptide NEAAINELMEDLDTNVDK (protein S100-A9) which had been placed in reserve during the first pass. De novo only peptides were considered last in the selection process for all organs, resulting in none of them being selected for synthesis. The described process led to a diverse set of 52 peptide marker candidates from 35 different proteins being selected for synthesis (Fig. 1, “Selection 2”), with a total of 20 peptides remaining in reserve (Table 2).

Our findings regarding potential target proteins in liver are in good agreement with those of Stachniuk, Trzpił, Kozub, Montowska and Fornal (2023) and Stachniuk, Trzpił, Montowska, Fornal (2023), who found liver-specific peptides in cooked liver of pig, chicken, and rabbit, which were not detectable in the corresponding cooked meat nor in cooked liver tissue of a selection of other species. With the exception of dihydrodiol dehydrogenase, which does not seem to have been

reported by the authors, analogues of all of the remaining seven liver proteins identified in the current study were found in one or more cases as sources of heat-stable liver-specific peptides by Stachniuk, Trzpił, Kozub, Montowska and Fornal (2023) and Stachniuk, Trzpił, Montowska, Fornal (2023). We consider this a validation of our workflow thus far, including the results for heart, kidney, lung, and spleen, for which no direct comparison could be found in the literature. The fact that we found significantly fewer potential peptide markers can be explained by our inclusion of four additional bovine organs and bovine blood in the selection criteria at this stage.

3.3. Confirmation of sequence identity and migration to triple quadrupole instrumentation

The MRM and sMRM analyses from this point onwards were performed using a QTrap detector, which was configured to act like a regular TQ-MS. Separate MRM methods were assembled for the five organs, containing five mass transitions with optimised MS parameters for each marker candidate except AADNIGYPVMIR (carbamoyl-phosphate synthase [ammonia], mitochondrial), for which only four mass transitions were available. To confirm the sequence identity of the investigated peptides, a spiking experiment was performed, using the synthesised peptides as the known reference sequences (Section 2.6). In the case of QAEEISAK, spiking of the sample with the synthesised reference greatly shifted the peak area ratios towards those of the pure QAEEISAK reference. Based on this evidence, it was concluded that the sequence assigned to this peptide was likely incorrect. Since it was the worst performing of the nine marker candidates for heart in terms of peak area, it was discarded without further investigation. The spleen peptide VPPASALR (peptidoglycan recognition protein 1 precursor) showed poor chromatographic behaviour (peak widths ≥ 60 s) and was likewise discarded because four alternatives targeting this protein were available. The identities of the remaining 50 candidates were confirmed in the experiment. For each peptide, the three mass transitions with the highest observed intensity were used as the basis for the sMRM method, except in the case of LNDGHFIPVLGFGTFAPR (dihydrodiol dehydrogenase 3), where an unseparated interference on the second most intensive transition resulted in the first, third and fourth mass transition being used. From this data, a single sMRM method was assembled, containing the remaining 50 peptide marker candidates as well as two control markers each for alfalfa, bovine blood, and all relevant types of meat (Section 2.6).

3.4. Tissue- and species-selectivity

While the peptide marker candidates had already been screened for tissue-selectivity using the QToF data, this point had to be revisited. In the data-dependent acquisition mode used, only a limited number of the most intensive signals at any given point in the analysis can be assessed by the instrument (Bilbao et al., 2015), allowing for the possibility that a peptide may have been overshadowed by other signals, potentially leading to false-negative findings and thus rendering the QToF data too unreliable for a final assessment of tissue-selectivity. Similarly, negative testing against the species from the exclusion list (Section 2.4.2) had at this point only extended to a BLAST database search, the results of which were inherently limited by the species coverage, completeness, and accuracy of the searched database. The QTrap instrument, set up to capture all transitions of interest via sMRM, was therefore used to further investigate the tissue- and species-selectivity of the peptide marker candidates.

Table 3

Comparison of peptide peak areas between bovine individuals. For individuals B1–B5, the average relative peak areas (n = 2, each) are provided as a percentage of the maximum average peak area (100) among individuals B1–B5 for each peptide in its primary target tissue. The relative standard deviation (sd [%], corresponding average not shown) was calculated from the listed values, excluding those highlighted in black. Values for tissue set A (individuals A1/A2) show the relative peak area (n = 1) related to the maximum average peak area of individuals B1–B5. Peptides are listed in ascending order of relative standard deviation, grouped by target tissue and target protein.

target	sequence	relative (average) peak area for set/individual:					sd [%]	protein		
		A	B1	B2	B3	B4			B5	
heart	VYLFELR	125	95	90	90	98	100	4.8	myosin-binding protein C, cardiac-type	
	IMDAQTTFAGGYR	95	90	84	91	100	94	6.4		
	SIFTVEGAER	71	76	84	86	100	89	10		
	TSLAGGSR	80	57	88	70	65	100	23		
	ELWQNIYDLEAEK	76	83	93	93	100	98	7.0		
kidney	SGGSTAGDTPAPPVPR ¹	84	84	80	88	100	87	8.5	troponin I, cardiac muscle	
	YENVQPAGSFK	73	81	66	83	86	100	15	serine dehydratase-like	
	ETVLDIVPTDIHQK	86	83	64	70	77	100	18	fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase 1	
	ATVLLADINDFSTVNDVYK	79	71	67	62	74	100	20	2-iminobutanoate/2-iminopropanoate deaminase	
	MILQNYTSLR	58	67	60	50	61	100	28	acyl-coenzyme A synthetase ACSM1, mitochondrial	
liver	YGGSYFPK	108	42	32	80	100	35	53	glycine amidinotransferase, mitochondrial precursor	
	FSLDQLITHVPLEK	84	98	58	100	90	79	20	alcohol dehydrogenase 1C	
	AADNIGYPVMIR	124	100	56	99	66	73	25	carbamoyl-phosphate synthase [ammonia], mitochondrial	
	SVTEFGNDTVTSTMTK ¹	26	54	52	79	63	100	29	fatty acid-binding protein, liver	
	lung	SPEENEAIVSIVK ¹	5	3	100	93	90	89	5.3	pulmonary surfactant-associated protein A precursor
HQVLQSQGVLR ¹		5	4	85	87	79	100	10		
VFSTNGQSVNFDAIK ¹		n.d.	n.d.	88	84	100	76	11		
VGGHIAAPR ¹		7	6	87	71	84	100	14		
LQGSVLAVGEK ¹		7	4	41	39	83	100	46		
TGLFTLHSELMVTPAR		26	24	74	70	100	89	17	advanced glycosylation end product-specific receptor precursor	
QSSSTSSFGMGGGSMR		18	25	83	65	100	79	18	keratin, type I cytoskeletal 19	
SSYGAPVGTGIR	36	48	68	61	100	65	24	keratin, type II cytoskeletal 7		
spleen	YTLNILEDIGGGQK	108	98	98	100	98	89	4.5	plastin-2	
	GSVDEEMLELR ²	120	96	100	96	90	89	4.9		
	VPVDWSR ²	86	97	100	89	90	86	6.3		
	EITENLMTTGDLDDQDGK ²	70	83	96	100	91	93	6.9		

¹ Peptide from Durose and Billett (2010); ² peptide evaluated during second workflow pass; n.d.: not detected.

3.4.1. Tissue-selectivity

Tissue-selectivity testing within *Bos taurus* was conducted using bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, spleen, as well as beef, and blood from six individuals each, whereby the first tissue set (A) was made up of tissues from two individuals (A1 and A2), with the remaining five sets stemming from single individuals (B1–B5). Alfalfa was also included to verify its ability to serve as a positive control in later experiments (Section 2.6). Tissue set A (heart, kidney, liver, beef, and blood: individual A1; lung, and spleen: individual A2) was analysed in an initial experiment, the results of which prompted the second pass of the workflow as described in Section 3.2, whereafter set A was analysed a second time for the additional peptide marker candidates found during the second pass. At this point, the first and second pass merged. Upon analysis of the additional five individuals (B1–B5), it was found that two of the six lung samples (A and B1) showed drastically lower abundance of all peptides present compared to the remaining four lung samples (Table 3). This affected all monitored peptides to various degrees, including one of the universal meat markers incidentally also found in lung (data not shown), which suggested that the issue was caused by a problem in sample preparation. Qualitatively, all lung samples were in agreement with each other, except regarding VFSTNGQSVNFDAIK (pulmonary surfactant-associated protein A precursor), which did not rise to the level of detectability in the two affected lung samples. Since it was the least sensitive of the peptide marker candidates for lung, this was not surprising. Due to this, and due to the results of the other four lungs being in very good agreement with each other also regarding peak areas, the peak area results of the two affected lungs were ignored in quantitative considerations.

Of the total number of 50 investigated peptide marker candidates (first pass: 42, second pass: 8), 24 were discarded (23 due to being found in beef or blood, and VNDDTIVSWNETLK (plastin-2) due to displaying a pronounced carry-over effect, which disqualified it for reasons of practicality). Regarding the qualitative detection of the remaining 26 peptides, the six individuals were in very good agreement

with each other. Exceptions were found in cases of low peak areas, where peptides fell below the S/N threshold in some individuals. The peptides YENVQPAGSFK (serine dehydratase-like), QSSSTSSFGMGGGSMR (keratin, type I cytoskeletal 19), and EITENLMTTGDLDDQDGK (plastin-2) were each detected, in addition to other matrices, as traces in single liver samples. While for QSSSTSSFGMGGGSMR and EITENLMTTGDLDDQDGK at least trace signals well below the S/N threshold were detectable in other liver samples, no such traces were found of YENVQPAGSFK. Since the latter peptide belongs to an enzyme, it is possible that this finding was the result of a difference in gene expression between the individuals due to a difference in metabolic activity. Table 3 shows relative peak areas in the primary target matrices for the six individuals, with standard deviation calculated for individuals B1–B5. Because the results for tissue set A were obtained as single injections in a two-part experiment, and a considerable time apart from those of individuals B1–B5, they were not factored into calculations and are provided for comparison only. In general, peptides targeting enzymes tended towards higher variability, indicated by a higher relative standard deviation. It is assumed that true biological differences between the individuals were the main cause, as enzyme concentrations are expected to vary from animal to animal. Peptides targeting the same protein showed comparable variability among each other, with the exception of TSLAGGSR (myosin-binding protein C, cardiac-type) and LQGSVLAVGEK (pulmonary surfactant-associated protein A precursor). One possible explanation for the variability of the former is offered by the fact that it is preceded and followed by multiple possible cleavage positions for trypsin in the target protein, potentially requiring multiple cuts to release the sequence of interest (...RR TSLAGGSR R...). Sun et al. (2021) found in their study that the frequency of additional lysine (K) or arginine (R) N-terminal of a monitored cleavage site was increased in peptides with missed cleavages. In the case of LQGSVLAVGEK (...LR LQGSVLAVGEK VF...) the reason for the deviation remains unclear. Since HQVLQSQGVLR and VFSTNGQSVNFDAIK, both showing much lower relative standard deviations, are reportedly located

Table 4

Occurrence of peptide signals (S/N ratio ≥ 3) in pure organ matrices (he, ki, li, sp: n=6; lu: n=4), and in organ-adulterated beef matrix consisting to 10% (w/w) of the indicated bovine organs (n=2). Organ-adulterated beef matrices were analysed raw and after cooking (30 min, 100 °C). The heat map illustrates for each peptide the relative average peak area in a matrix as a percentage of the maximum average peak area (100) of that peptide across all five matrices, separately for the three matrix categories. Peptides are listed in ascending order of retention time, grouped by target tissue and target protein.

label	NCBI accession	pure organ matrix					raw 10 % (w/w) organ-adulterated beef matrix					cooked 10 % (w/w) organ-adulterated beef matrix				
		he	ki	li	lu	sp	he	ki	li	lu	sp	he	ki	li	lu	sp
heart1	NP_001070004.1	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-
heart3		100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-
heart4		100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-
heart5		100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-
heart2		NP_001035607.1	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-
heart6	NP_777196.1	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-
kidney1	NP_001092465.1	-	100	1 ^a	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-
pmc3	NP_001029619.1	-	100	76	1	<1	c									
pmc4	NP_001029380.1	-	100	22	13	14	c									
kidney/liver1	NP_001039343.1	-	100	73	-	-	-	65	100	-	-	-	69	100	-	-
kidney/liver2	NP_777107.1	-	100	74	2	-	-	73	100	-	-	-	65	100	-	-
liver1	NP_787011.1	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-
liver2	NP_001179187.1	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-
liver3	NP_001193316.1	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-
lung1	NP_001071306.2	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-
lung4		-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-
lung5		-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-
pmc1		-	-	-	100	-	c									
pmc2		-	-	-	100 ^b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
lung2	NP_001015600.1	-	19	5 ^a	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-
lung3	NP_001039876.1	-	-	3	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-
lung6	NP_776407.1	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100	-
spleen/lung1	NP_001029892.1	-	5 ^b	4 ^b	27	100	-	-	-	30	100	-	-	-	28	100
spleen/lung2		6 ^b	6	4	30	100	-	-	-	31	100	-	-	-	37	100
spleen1		-	-	-	11 ^b	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100
spleen2		-	-	6 ^{a,b}	23	100	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	100

heat map key:

>0-	>10-	>20-	>30-	>40-	>50-	>60-	>70-	>80-	>90-
≤10	≤20	≤30	≤40	≤50	≤60	≤70	≤80	≤90	≤100

^a signal observed in only one pure organ sample; ^b signal identity unconfirmed by peak area ratios (>15% deviation from spiked sample in all occurrences); ^c results inconclusive due to carry-over or interference; “-” = not detected. Organ abbreviations: he = heart, ki = kidney, li = liver, lu = lung, sp = spleen.

directly before and directly after LQGSVLAVGEK in the sequence of the targeted protein, the observed deviation cannot be explained by missed cleavages. Our results for the tissue-selectivity of the peptides from Durose and Billett (2010) are consistent with the implicit findings of the authors that these peptides are tissue-specific within the range of samples they analysed. On average, all 26 peptides shown in Table 3 were most abundant in their primary target tissue in which they were first detected, with 11 of those peptides showing cross-selectivity for at least one other organ. Some of the detected signals showed peak area ratio deviations in excess of 15% in every individual they were detected in. The corresponding peptides were still counted as present in those tissues, since the deviation was deemed plausible on account of their low signal intensity making them more susceptible to interferences. More detailed information on the occurrence and relative abundance of the peptides in pure organs can be found in the first section of Table 4.

3.4.2. Species-selectivity

To verify the results of the in silico BLAST species-selectivity testing, separate pool samples consisting of meat from three individuals were prepared for chicken, goat, horse, pig, sheep, and turkey. Five additional pools consisting of other food ingredients (including egg, milk, herbs, spices, and grains) were also prepared, bringing the total number of individual animal and vegetable samples to 43 (Section 2.6). All pools were formulated under consideration of the estimated protein content of each component, so that each component of a pool contributed roughly the same absolute amount of protein to the total of that pool. None of the 26 peptide marker candidates listed in Table 3 were detected in any of the pools. The positive control alfalfa, which had been added to each pool sample before protein extraction at a level below that of the pool component with the lowest protein contribution,

was detected in each case. Hence, the 26 peptide marker candidates were considered species-specific within the scope of this work.

3.5. Detectability and heat-stability in a model beef matrix

A simple model beef matrix was formulated (Section 2.2.2) to investigate the detectability and heat-stability of the peptide marker candidates under more realistic conditions, and to elucidate the practical implications of the cross-selectivities reported in Section 3.4.1. Beef and bovine organs were blended together to form highly processed, organ-adulterated model matrices. An unadulterated sample of the beef served as the control (Section 2.6). The adulteration level had to be selected such that all peptides could reasonably be expected to remain detectable in their raw adulterated matrices with the currently unoptimised protocol, or no insight into their heat-stability would be gained. A level of 10% (w/w) was chosen based on the extrapolation of previous peak area data.

To investigate the heat-stability of the peptide marker candidates, one portion of each matrix was cooked for 30 min at 100 °C in a water bath (Section 2.2.2), producing fully cooked samples to simulate food processing. The amount of sample material used for protein extraction was increased from 5 mg to 25 mg in order to partially compensate for the lower amount of organ tissue in the samples. An increase to 50 mg, to fully compensate, was outside the scope of this work, since it would have necessitated the adjustment of the sample preparation protocol. From the resulting data, four peptide marker candidates could not be conclusively evaluated for the purposes of this work. Pmc1 (VGGHIAAPR; pulmonary surfactant-associated protein A precursor) was subject to interference on all mass transitions in this experiment, as it was not significantly retained by the chromatographic column ($t_R = 0.44$ min). Determining its presence was impossible for this reason.

Fig. 3. Comparison of chromatograms of raw and cooked organ-adulterated samples. Shown are selected example sMRM chromatograms of pure and organ-adulterated beef matrices (10% w/w) raw and cooked (30 min, 100 °C). Total LC runtime: 28 min. * incompletely separated interferences originating from beef; blue = raw; red = cooked. For adulterated matrices, only the mass transitions of the peptides indicated as present in Table 4 are shown. For the unadulterated beef, all transitions of the adulterated matrices are shown for comparison. The chromatograms shown are reconstructions based on exported original signal data, which is provided as original chromatograms in Supplementary Figures S3–S8. X-axis labels apply to columns, y-axis labels apply to rows.

The increase in interference compared to previous experiments was probably due to the increased amount of sample material used for protein extraction. Pmc2 (VFSTNGQSVNFDAIK), targeting the same protein as pmc1, was considered not detected, since its signal intensity was reduced below the detectability threshold (S/N ratio < 3). This was in line with previous observations regarding the relative sensitivity of this peptide (Section 3.4.1). The peptides labelled pmc3 (ETVLDIVPTDI-HQK; fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase 1) and pmc4 (ATVLLADINDFSTVND-VYK; 2-iminobutanoate/2-iminopropanoate deaminase), with kidney as their primary target, showed a pronounced carry-over effect for the first time in this experiment, rendering their results unusable. Additional measurements after the replacement of the pre-column in the HPLC system suggest that this may be connected to the age of the used columns. Further investigation of pmc1 – pmc4 is required and is going to be carried out as part of future research.

All remaining 22 peptides were detected in the raw and cooked organ-adulterated beef matrices, whereas they were not detected in the pure beef control. Their suitability as peptide markers was at this point considered confirmed, and they were labelled according to their selectivity apparent in the beef matrices and in ascending order of retention time. Fig. 3 shows a comparison of selected example chromatograms for the raw and cooked organ-adulterated beef matrices. Although each of them represents only a single injection, they nevertheless illustrate the qualitative picture and provide an indication of the trends. Cooking resulted in some noticeable decreases (e.g. kidney/liver2) or increases (e.g. heart2), while the intensities of unseparated interferences generally decreased. Peptides targeting the same protein showed collective tendencies to decrease or increase, in line with expectations. Both the number and extent of cross-selectivities decreased compared to pure organ matrices, likely due to the decrease in organ-related extracted weight (pure organs: 5 mg; adulterated matrices: effectively 2.5 mg) and the impact of beef as the main matrix constituent. Table 4 shows the occurrence and relative abundance of the markers in the adulterated matrices, together with the situation in pure organs as portrayed by the results of the tissue-selectivity testing described in Section 3.4.1. Organ-specific peptide markers appear available for all five organs in the adulterated matrices, with the four peptides kidney/liver1 (YGGSYFPK), kidney/liver2 (MILQQNYTSLR), spleen/lung1 (GSVSDEEMLELR), and spleen/lung2 (YTLNILEDIGGGQK) being selective for a pair of organs each. However, the fact that spleen1 (VPVDWSR) and spleen2 (EITENLMTTGDLQDQDGK) target the same protein as spleen/lung1 and spleen/lung2 according to the BLAST results, in conjunction with signals for all four peptides having been found in pure lung and spleen, means that the organ-specificity shown by spleen1 and spleen2 is, in all likelihood, only due to them being less sensitive. The situation in pure organ matrices needs to be kept in mind for all markers. Any cross-selectivity observed there may become relevant again, for instance due to method optimisation or higher adulteration levels. In addition to the four aforementioned spleen and spleen/lung peptides, also kidney1 (YENVQPAGSFK), kidney/liver2 (MILQQNYTSLR), lung2 (QSSSTSSFGMGGGSMR), and lung3 (SSY-GAPVGTGIR) may lose selectivity with increasing sensitivity or peptide abundance. The reversal in main target tissue of kidney/liver1 and kidney/liver2 compared to pure organ matrices was due to the fact that only organs of one individual were used in the production of the organ-adulterated beef matrices, whereas the pure organ results for kidney and liver represent the average of six individuals.

Overall, the 22 peptide markers published in this work can be regarded as both heat-stable and as detectable in a highly processed model beef matrix. The detection of 10% offal adulteration may already prove useful in fraud prevention, but lower detection limits of 1% to 2% will ultimately be required to address all expected fraud scenarios. Any future optimisation efforts must include a re-evaluation of marker selectivity, because an increase in sensitivity could uncover currently unknown cross-selectivities. Our goal of identifying at least three peptide markers per organ, targeting at least two proteins, was achieved for

bovine heart (6/3; peptides/proteins), liver (3/3), and lung (6/4), with organ-specific peptide markers being available for each. While kidney and spleen were more limited in the number of available markers and targeted proteins, a basis for their detection was still provided through peptides for kidney (1/1), kidney/liver (2/2), spleen/lung (2/1) and spleen (2/1), with spleen/lung and spleen markers targeting the same protein. The reserve peptides for heart (13), liver (3), kidney (3), and lung (1), in addition to the four remaining peptide marker candidates (pmc1 – pmc4), may in future works also be investigated to increase the number of available peptides or targeted proteins. In particular, the peptide IPATIVLPEGTSVK would be a promising candidate, as it targets the same protein as kidney1.

4. Conclusion

This study presents 22 heat-stable peptide markers suitable as the basis for developing a method for the simultaneous detection of bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen in minced beef products. A multi-stage workflow involving untargeted and targeted MS/MS analyses was used to identify and investigate a large number of peptides and select those most suitable for the purpose. This resulted in the discovery of 17 new peptide markers and the confirmation of five additional peptide markers known from the literature: heart (6), kidney (1), kidney/liver (2), liver (3), lung (6), spleen/lung (2), spleen (2). Four more peptide marker candidates are pending final evaluation. All evaluated peptide markers were heat-stable and detectable in a highly processed model beef matrix at a 10% (w/w) organ adulteration level. Unlike studies focused on single tissues, this work simultaneously addressed five organs and can thereby offer the first marker set for the detection of multiple bovine offal tissues in processed beef. The goal of identifying at least three peptide markers per organ, targeting at least two proteins, was achieved for bovine heart, liver, and lung, with organ-specific peptide markers being available for each. Kidney and spleen were more limited in the number of available markers and targeted proteins, but a basis for their detection was still provided. At the 10% (w/w) adulteration level, a reliable differentiation of all five organs through a purely qualitative approach appears possible with the current protocol, although higher adulteration levels may also require the use of quantitative relationships between markers to identify spleen in the presence of lung, or kidney in the presence of liver. Regarding the species-selectivity of the markers it must be noted that our assessment relies in part on protein database entries, which may be incomplete, contain errors, or be unavailable altogether for some species. For this reason, we recommend that the reader confirms the specificity of the markers themselves, especially if their scenario differs from those covered in this work. In particular, we would like to highlight the matter of organ tissues from other species, which were not included in the testing and would require additional attention. The next objective is to use the peptide markers described in this work as the basis for developing a rapid and sensitive new LC-MS/MS method for the simultaneous detection of bovine heart, kidney, liver, lung, and spleen in processed and cooked beef products for use in food control laboratories.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thomas Braunersreuther: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Dagmar A. Brüggemann:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Andreas Römpf:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Wolfgang Jira:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2025.144383>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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